

Operational Policy Recommendations

MAY 2025

EUROPEAN IDENTITY THEFT OBSERVATORY SYSTEM

FUNDED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
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Policy Recommendations

- 1** Clearly identify the gaps in EU Legislation regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence for identity related crimes online, in particular deepfakes for fraudulent & deceiving purposes (i.e. Deepfakes, Botnets), not only for deterrence but also for prosecution.

Define Online Identity Theft (OIDT) clearly within all EU member states and incorporate AI-related identity theft offenses and cases **in order to harmonize legal responses per EU member state.**

- 2** Foster collaboration between LEAs, financial institutions (banks), information service providers.

Create **mechanisms for enhanced cooperation** to develop technological tools to detect and prevent identity related crimes, emphasizing **data security and real-time information exchange.**

- 3** LEAs to increase public awareness of identity theft prevention.

LEAs to implement more EU-wide campaigns educating citizens on the **risks of OIDT** and the **importance of safeguarding personal data online.**

- 4** Establish and train specialized units within LEAs on OIDT technologies.

Equip LEAs with **the necessary AI tools** (deepfakes detection tools, social botnets detection tools) and expertise to recognize, investigate, and respond to Identity Related crimes online.

- 5** LEAs to support and empower online identity theft fraud victims.

Enhance victim support mechanisms and ensure LEAs are equipped to address the **psychosocial impacts** of identity theft on affected individuals. Public sharing of periodic internal reports on the most frequent OIDT case studies and profile of the victims.

- 6** Need for more comprehensive EU surveys and official statistics on the topic of **identity-related crimes online.** This exercise should aim at **providing detailed information over each specific crime** falling under the umbrella term of online identity theft.

Policy Implications

1 Legislation that defines OI DT uniformly across member states would close legal loopholes and enable **faster cross-border investigations**.

2 Enhanced collaboration between LEAs, banks, and telecoms would streamline **information sharing**, making it more effective in identifying and preventing OI DT crimes.

3 **Increased public awareness** would reduce individual vulnerabilities.

4 **Specialized LEA training** would improve crime detection and victim support.

5 The proposed measures and mechanisms to support victims, require consistent **funding, cross-sector commitment**, and **standardized EU training frameworks** to ensure practical and uniform application across all member states.

6 Provides policymakers and stakeholders with **reliable data to craft targeted interventions**.

Enhances **understanding of trends and impacts** of identity-related crimes, enabling tailored prevention and response strategies. Strengthens collaboration across EU Member States by establishing **shared benchmarks and metrics**.

Project Details

Project Name

The European Identity Theft
Observatory System (EITHOS)

Coordinator

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CERTH

Programme - call topic

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Online identity theft is countered

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3 years
October 2022 - September 2025

Budget

€ 2,996,141.25

Social Media

EITHOS_EU

eithos_eu_project

Eithos - Horizon Europe project

EITHOS_EU

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